

(Grammatical Judgments On Similarities, Between Theory And Practice) (Provisions Of The Case Based On Similar)

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: August 03, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: March 06, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Similarity, Similarity, Adverb, Distinction, Grammatical Provisions</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6332909</p>	<p><i>Arabic grammar is in many phenomena, including similarity. The similarity plays an important role in linking the sections of grammar, including the case section. I found that it has a similarity between distinctions, predicate, adjective, adverb, and object. Many of its rulings were built as a result of this similarity, and I have concluded that the rules that he acquired differ according to the strength The similarity between him and the suspect, and in general, the phenomenon of similarity has an impact on the establishment of many grammatical provisions, so it was necessary to research this phenomenon and know everything related to it</i></p> <p><i>This research came with the help of scientific and academic curricula in its presentation, with the help of old and modern sources and references, and with the help of thought, consideration and meditation in the Arabic language and the statements of those around it. The object and the object of it is the circumstance and the case similar to the predicate, the epithet and the distinction, and the research has shown these rulings from all their scientific aspects.</i></p>

Introduction

Its definition: "The case is a description of the form of the subject or the object, and as for the pronunciation of it, it is an accusative that comes after a knowledge of which the speech has been completed, and that is the meaning of the denial: 62).

And Ibn Babshadh defined him: The sixth mentions the statement about the body of the subject and the object, transmitted, estimated, Muwatta, or confirmed. Like: Zaid came laughing, and this is Zaid hunting tomorrow, and this is a book that is confirmed in the Arabic tongue, and it is the truth confirming" (Ibn Babshadh: 2/310).

It is a condition of the case that it be a noun, derivative, or interpreted by a derivative; Because it is a description, and the description is only a derivative, and that it comes after knowledge after the completion of the speech, and that it is not for what has passed, nor for what is to come, and everything that came in contrary to these conditions is interpreted, (Ibn Al-Atheer: 1/186).

Just as the situation has conditions, it has provisions, including what is built on the similarity between it and other sections of grammar, so it has taken a chance in similar effect in general, and object in particular, as well as adverb of time, distinction, predicate, and epithet. We will mention the similarity of each one of them, with a mention of the provisions that follow.

1- Similar to the case:

The case is similar to the object in general, not restricted by a letter, as it is a virtue that comes after the completion of the speech, just as the object is a virtue that comes after the completion of the speech, so both of them come after the completion of the sentence from the predicate and the predicate to it, so your saying: Zaid gold, a complete sentence, the predicate is "hit", The ascribed to him is "Zayd." If you say: Zaid went quickly, then "Speed" came after the completion of the sentence, then it is a virtue, as you said: Zaid hit Omar, because "Amra" came after the sentence was satisfied with its two basic corners, and in addition to that, in the verb is evidence of The subject, as it contains evidence of the case, as the agent in the instant is a real verb, just as the agent of the object is a real verb, so your saying: Zaid came riding, then "rider" is set up with "came," as well as your saying: Zaid struck Omar, for "Amra" is set. By "beating" but rather erect, because it is similar to the object from the faces that we mentioned, (Al-Mubarrad: 3/260, Ibn Al-Siraj: 1/213, Al-Zamakhshari: 89).

2- Similar to the subject:

The adverb has a special resemblance to the accusative, as for its resemblance to the accusative in that it is a virtue after the completion of the speech, and the verb dispenses with its subject, and the other thing is that the adverb does not appear with it "in" the ability, so do not say: Zaid went in haste, in your saying: Zaid went quickly And the object of it does not appear with it "in" so do not say: Zaid struck Amr in your saying: Zaid beat Omar, and among the rulings that were arranged for this similarity (Al-Jundi: 1/517):

1- The permissibility of the case being preceded by its agent: the case is never established and its rightful one is either an act of conduct, or what is in the course of the action of the nouns, such as the noun of the subject, the noun of the object, or something in the meaning of the act, if the agent of it is an act of conduct, or something similar to the act of traits; It is permissible to put it before its agent, as you say: With laughter, Zaid came, and Amr came in haste, and it is permissible to precede him over his managing agent. Because of the similarity between it and the object of it, it is permissible to take it before its agent, so she says: Omar hit Zaid, and examples of that are:

The Almighty said: {their eyes should be humbled when they come out of the graves} (Al-Qamar:7).
frothing that comes to mind that he has not seen me... and if my flesh is empty for him, he trembles
So “frothing” is present, and the actant verb treats him “notifies.”

2- The necessity of setting the adverb: Al-Baqouli sees that the adverb is based on a similarity between it and the object in particular, as it is a virtue after the completion of the speech from the verb and the subject, and also the object is a virtue after the completion of the speech (Al-Baqouli: 462).

Al-Suyuti said, “They differed from which section of the accusative case, so it was said accusative accusative, and it was said accusative that is similar to the accusative, and it is more likely” (Suyuti: 2/294).

3- Similar to the case:

Most of the grammarians went to the effect that the situation is similar to the object in it, so Hebron (may God have mercy on him) sees that the situation is similar to the circumstance in that the action takes place, in your saying: Zaid went quickly, for going is an event that occurred in the case of speeding (Al-Khalil: 70).

Sibawayh has stated that he is afflicted with it when he said: “Chapter of what is erected from the sources, because it is a situation in which the matter occurred, so erect because the command is signed in it” (Sibawayh: 1 / 370).

Al-Mubarrad believes that the case is an object in it and is not similar to it (Al-Mubarrad: 4/166).

And Ibn Al-Sarraj went to the effect that it is the same as the accusative, (Ibn Al-Sarraj: 1/218).

And the Persian sees that the situation is more like the circumstance of time in particular, so you say: Zaid came quickly, and Amr came riding, it is in the meaning of your saying: Zaid came in the case of speed, and at the time of speeding, and Amr came in the case of riding, it is similar to the circumstances of time, (Al-Farsi: 199) .

The adverb is similar to the adverb in that it includes the meaning of “in” just as the adverb includes the meaning of “in,” and that the verb occurs in a specific situation as it also occurs in a specific time and place. A specific time and a specific place is like your saying: Amr came to me in the morning, for Omar’s coming in the morning time, and if he did not mention the circumstance, it is a reasonable thing, as the event is not without a specific form, at a specific time and a specific place, and the situation is transitional just as the circumstance be movable. (Ibn Abi Al-Rabi’: 511)

The situation is like this, it is necessary, but it is most likely to move, and from that they say: God created the giraffe with its hands longer than its legs, so “longer” is a predicate condition that is necessary; Because the length is fixed and does not change (Ibn Malik: 2/322, Ibn Hisham: 2/464).

Contrasting the case with the circumstance in that it comes as necessary, this does not mean that there is no amount of similarity, for if the thing is similar to the thing from all sides, it is the same, so there is no need to form a semi-relationship, the case took a fortune from the effect in it, especially the circumstance of time, as well as the effect By it, it does not run through the course of the object at all, just as it does not run through the course of the object at all, and therefore its rulings were acquired according to the strength and abundance of the resemblance.

1- Permissibility of applying the meanings of verbs in them:

It is permissible at once to work the meaning of the verb in it, such as: Perhaps Zaid is in the house standing, and this Amr is riding, for the agent is immediately “standing”, and “riding” is the meaning of the verb contained in “perhaps” and “this”, and from that is the Almighty’s saying : {And this is Ali a sheikh} (Hud: 72), so “sheikh” is an established state, and the accusative factor in it is the meaning of the verb contained in “this”, and its appraisal is “pointed” (Al-Jurjani: 1/674,673,672). The meanings of non-pure verbs as they work in circumstances, such as your saying: This is added to the house in the morning, for “Morning is an adverb of time that is set to work.” This “contains the meaning of the verb “refer”, and it should be noted that the circumstances in which the meanings of verbs work, whether they are advanced or delayed. , but the case is not permissible to take precedence over its moral factor, and this is due to the fact that the situation is “similar” and the circumstance is “similar to it”, meaning that the circumstance is an origin in that, and the situation is a branch of it, and the branches must deviate from the origins in addition to the verb weakens with the progress made on it. And the evidence for that is an established connection with the preposition, which says: You honored Zaid, and if you presented it, you said: You have honored Zaid, as in the Almighty’s saying: {If you cross the vision} (Yusuf: 43).

The other matter is that the case is more like the object of it, and the object is that if it precedes its action, the action of the verb in it is doubled even though the action is a strong factor, and that is towards the Almighty’s

saying: {And both are the most beautiful promises of Allah} (An-Nisa: 95), Ibn Aamir read with the lifting of “every”. And if the verb did not work in the object and the case was similar to the object, it would have been better for the meanings of the verbs not to work in them if they take precedence over their moral factor, (Ibn Abi Al-Rabi’: 512, 513).

Sibawayh said: “Know that it is not said that a man is standing in it. If someone says: I place him in the same position as riding in the passing of Zayd, and riding in the passing of a man, it will be said to him: He is similar to him in analogy, because in it there is the status of bitter, but they hated that in what was not in the act, because in it and its sisters They do not act like a verb, not a verb, but they have brought down the status of what the noun is indispensable for in the verb. So pay it as the Arabs did, and it is acceptable” (Sibawayh: 2/124).

Al-Fara’ (Al-Fara’: 2/425), Al-Akhfash, and Ibn Malik (Ibn Malik: 2/346) went to the permissibility of giving precedence to the spiritual factor, citing the reading of Ibn Aamer (Ibn Khalawayh: 131), in the Almighty’s saying: {And the heavens are folded in His right hand} (Az-Zumar: 67).

And Ibn Abbas, may God be pleased with him, said: “This verse was revealed and the Messenger of God, may God bless him and grant him peace, was hiding in Makkah.”

The Rahat of Ibn Kuz Muhaqibi had their armor among them... and the Rahat of Rabi’ah bin Hadhar.

So, “folders” are a situation that is erected ahead of its moral factor “in its oath”, and “hidden” is a state that is erected before its moral factor “in Mecca”, and the poet’s saying, “Mahbabi of their arms” is a state that has preceded its moral factor that is included in the semi-sentence “them”, (the fur). : 1/358, Ibn Malik: 2/346).

2- Refusal to initiate action:

When the situation resembled the circumstance, it was forbidden to act in it. Because he refrains from acting in the circumstances, as the situation in which the action and the meaning of the act works, and the initiation does not work in it; Because the envelope does not work in the beginning, so it was carried on the envelope; Because the suspect does not strengthen the strength of the suspect, and the branches must deviate from the principles, and the circumstances in which the meanings of non-pure verbs work are delayed, or preceded, while they do not act immediately except in the event of their delay; Because the branch deviates from the original in these rulings, the suspect does not acquire all the rules of the suspect, but rather according to the extent and strength of the similarity (Ibn Abi Al-Rabi’: 528).

3- Mandatory accusation:

The case is stabilized for himself to circumvent when he sees this, including Hebron, may God have mercy on him. Already and do if the act has fallen, the disease occurred when the act has occurred, even if the case is active as a necessity did not do that he is going to go to him because the launch of an emotion and the emotion is never exceeded because you do not say the man, (Hebron: 70).

4- It is permissible for the present sentence to be free from the possessive pronoun:

The purpose of the return in the current sentence is to link it to what preceded it, and this link is either the waw, or the pronoun, and it may be devoid of the return in analogy to the circumstance, so it says: I came to you and Zaid standing, and I met you and Amr is a starting point, the poet said, (Amru al-Qais: 19):

And he had taken lunch, and the birds were in their cradles... with a skeleton in place.

His saying “and the bird is in its nicknames” is a current sentence devoid of a pronoun that refers to the person of the situation, but it is permissible to do it in the same way as the circumstance, so it is as you say: I met you at the time of Omar’s sitting, and you say: Zaid came while the sun was rising, it is as you said: Zaid came at the time of sunrise. It is permissible for the circumstance to dispense with the return, and the situation is very similar to the circumstance, it is permissible for him to do what is permissible for the suspect, (Ibn Ya’ish 2/33, 32, Ibn al-Hajeb 1/311).

5- Similar to the news:

The case is a piece of news, and that is why Sibawayh called it in more than one place news (Sibawayh: 2/ 87, 86), and the similarity of the case to the news is that the news is a statement about knowledge, or something close to knowledge as the owner of the situation is knowledge, and the news It is derived, transmitted, rigid, and imperative, and Ibn Ya’ish sees that the case is second news (Ibn Ya’ish: 2/17), so your saying: Zaid came riding, because the sentence included a report about Zaid coming in the event that he was riding, so the news is useful, and the situation is increasing. In the interest, and from here the son made him live a second news in the meaning, as the situation is a sentence, and the news is a sentence and the strength of this similarity, some of what is expressed at once may be expressed as news, it was read: {And this is my son, an elder} (Hud: 72), and this reading Ibn Masoud, Al-A’ mash, Abi and Al-Mutawa’i, (Al-Akbari 2/23), referred to “Sheikh” as a report, and the situation is a virtue, so it does not take the place of the intentional, but it may come in places closer to the news in reality and meaning, and from that the Almighty’s saying: {And if they rise to the Prayers rose up lazily} (An-Nisa: 142).

So “lazy” is a condition established, and it is a pillar here. Ibn Malik said: “The case is news in the meaning, and its owner is informing about it, so its origin is knowledge as the origin of the subject is knowledge, and as it is permissible to begin with the indefinite provided that the meaning is clear and the security of confusion, and it is not That is only with a justification.” (Ibn Malik: 2/331). From the foregoing, we find that the situation is similar

to the news in several aspects, and that its relationship to the news is a strong relationship, and grammarians have investigated the similarities and linked them, so they made some provisions of the case as a result of this similarity, including:

1- Denying the situation: the majority of grammarians believe that the situation must be insignificant; Because it is news from the news, and the news is denial, and the situation in which there is increased benefit, just as the news has benefit, and what came as knowledge is interpreted as they say: I sent her to the battle, that is: a battle, and alone I strive, that is: alone, and I passed them by the great crowd, that is: together, and permitted Yunus and the Baghdadis define it, towards: Zayd al-Rikab came, by analogy with what was heard (Al-Suyuti: 2/301). Al-Shatibi said: “The situation is a piece of news, so make it necessary to deny it, lest it be imagined that it is an epithet without a condition, and also, the condition is a virtue that is inherent in virtue, as there is no intention in speech at all. He deserves to be known, as there is no benefit in defining him, and other things deserved him from the waste because he was intentionally falling and taking the place of the doer, so it is permissible for him to come with knowledge, with this face of denial in the explanation. (Al-Shatibi: 3/433).

2- Definition of the owner of the case: the owner of the case is often knowledge; Because he is condemned, and the condition of the convict is knowledge; Because the ruling on the indefinite does not benefit most, just as the case is news in the meaning, and the news about the indefinite is not permissible, and there is no benefit in it often, and that the owner of the case is similar to the subject, and the situation is similar to the news, and the subject is judged, and the news is governed by it just as the case and its owner are likewise, and for this reason The majority of the case was that he was knowledgeable and his condition was unknown, and the person of the unknowing situation might come with a justification (Ibn Malik: 2/335, Abu Hayyan: 9/60, al-Sabban: 2/259) that brings him closer to knowledge as if he is singled out, preceded by denial, or preceded On his companion, from that the Almighty said: {in four days alike to those who ask} (Fussilat: 10), and from that: {And we destroyed no village without it having a known book} (Al-Hijr:4), and from it: In the house a man stood.

6- Similar case discrimination:

The similarity between the adverb and the distinction is multifaceted, so we see Sibawayh mentioned a facet that is that both of them are indefinite and the verb has been done in them (Sibawayh: 1 / 44, 45), and he did not mention the other places of similarity, and it is certainly not hidden from him, as the case in it is a statement and a revelation of the ambiguity The same applies to discrimination (Al-Jarjani: 1/675, 676), and Ibn Hisham (Ibn Hisham: 2/460_464) believes that discrimination is similar to the case in five aspects, and contradicts it in seven. Thumbs up.

The violations are:

- 1 - That the original in the instant is to be derivative, and the principle of discrimination is that it is rigid.
- 2- That the situation may not be spoken except with it towards the saying of the Most High: {And do not walk on the earth exultantly} (Luqman: 18).
- 3- The situation is clear to the authority, and the discrimination is self-explanatory.
- 4- The situation is multiple other than discrimination.
- 5- The adverb is singular, plural, and semi-sentence in contrast to discrimination, so it is only singular.
- 6- That the case is confirmed for its factor, unlike discrimination.
- 7- That the situation takes precedence over the disposing factor, and it is not permissible to discriminate in this according to the most correct one.

This similarity did not result in grammatical rulings, except that some grammarians mentioned that the case deserved to be denied; It is similar to discrimination in the aspects that we have mentioned, including Ibn al-Khabbaz when he says: “But it must be disavowed, because it resembles discrimination. Do you not see that if you say: Zaid came, is it possible for him to come with different types and characteristics?! If he says: Riding, between the appearance of coming Likewise, if he says: I have twenty, he assumes a number of genders, and if he says: A dirham, then he shows what the twenty fell on him” (Ibn Al-Khabbaz: 203).

Also, Ibn Yaish mentioned several explanations for his being nothing, including his similarity to discrimination (Ibn Yaish: 2/62).

7- Similar to the adjective:

The similarity of the case to the adjective is in that the case is an adjective in the meaning, and therefore one of its conditions was that it be a derivative as the adjective is also derived, and the adjective works in which a factor describes it just as the case in it is the worker in the owner of the case, except that his work is immediately on the path of virtue, and his work in the attribute As a matter of need, the case is similar to the adjective in a moral similarity, as both indicate something in its owner, and both are derived nouns, and the association of the adjective with the participle is similar to the link of the case with its owner, as the case comes singular, sentence and semi-sentence, as well as the epithet.

It is worth noting that the case differs from the adjective, in that it is a virtue that comes after the completion of the speech. As for the adjective, it follows its innuendo, a pillar, or a virtue.

These are the similarities between the adverb and the epithet, and the ruling that follows from this similarity: is the permissibility of multiple adverbs, as Ibn Malik says: "Previously, the adverb has a resemblance to a predicate and a resemblance to an epithet. Two cases upwards, and it will be said: Zaid came riding, leaving, and accompanying Omar." (Ibn Malik: 2/348).

From the words of Ibn Malik, we find that his resemblance to the predicate and the epithet made it multiple.

References:

- Origins in Grammar, Abu Bakr Muhammad bin Al-Sari bin Sahl Al-Nahwi, known as Ibn Al-Siraj (d. 316 AH), investigation: Abdul-Hussein Al-Fatli, Publisher: Al-Resala Foundation, Lebanon - Beirut, number of volumes: 3.
- The Minority in Explanation of the Mufassal, Taj Al-Din Ahmed bin Mahmoud bin Omar Al-Jundi (d. 700 AH), investigation by Dr. Mahmoud Ahmed Ali Abu Kittah Al-Darawish, Imam Muhammad bin Saud Islamic University, first edition, 1423 AH - 2003 AD.
- Al-Iddah Al-Addi, Abu Ali Al-Farsi (288-377 AH), investigation: Dr. Hassan Shazly Farhoud (College of Arts - University of Riyadh), Edition: First, 1389 AH - 1969 AD.
- Al-Badi' in the Science of Arabic, Majd Al-Din Abu Al-Saadat Al-Mubarak bin Muhammad bin Muhammad bin Muhammad bin Abdul Karim Al-Shaibani Al-Jazari Ibn Al-Atheer (d. 606 AH), investigation and study: Dr. Fathi Ahmed Ali Al-Din, Publisher: Umm Al-Qura University, Makkah Al-Mukarramah - Saudi Arabia, Edition: First, 1420 AH.
- Al-Basit fi Sharh Al-Zajji's Jamal, by Ibn Abi Al-Rabee' Obaid Allah bin Ahmad bin Obaid Allah Al-Qurashi Al-Ishbili Al-Sabti (d. 688 AH), investigation and study: Dr. Ayyad bin Eid Al-Thubby, Publisher: Dar Al-Gharb Al-Islami, Beirut _ Lebanon, Edition: First 1407 AH_ 1986AD .
- Guiding the Glory, Ahmed bin Al Hussein bin Al Khabbaz, study and investigation: a. Dr.. Fayez Zaki Muhammad Diab, Professor of Linguistics, Faculty of Arabic Language, Al-Azhar University, Origin of the investigation: Ph.D. Thesis - Faculty of Arabic Language, Al-Azhar University, Publisher: Dar Al-Salaam for Printing, Publishing, Distribution and Translation - Arab Republic of Egypt Edition: Second, 1428 AH - 2007AD.
- The Camel in Grammar, Abu Abd al-Rahman al-Khalil ibn Ahmad ibn Amr ibn Tamim al-Farahidi al-Basri (died 170 AH), investigation: Dr. Fakhr Al-Din Qabawah, Fifth Edition, 1416 AH 1995 AD.
- Diwan Al-Nabigha, Al-Nabigha Al-Dhibani, investigation: Muhammad Abu Al-Fadl Ibrahim, publisher: Dar Al-Maaref, edition: second.
- Diwan of Imru' al-Qays, Imru' al-Qays ibn Hajar ibn al-Harith al-Kindi, from Bani Akel al-Marar (died: 545 AD), taken care of by: Abd al-Rahman al-Mastawi, Publisher: Dar al-Maarifa - Beirut, Edition: Second, 1425 AH - 2004 AD, Number of Parts: 1.
- Diwan of Suwaid bin Abi Kahil Al-Yashkari (died about 60 AH), compiled and verified by: Shaker Al-Ashour, publisher Dar Sader _ Beirut, edition: 4th 1435 AH _ 2014 AD.
- Sharh Al-Lama', Abu Al-Hasan, Ali Bin Al-Hussein Al-Baqouli Al-Asfahani, investigation: Ibrahim Bin Muhammad Abu Ubadah, Publisher: Imam Muhammad Bin Saud Islamic University, Publication Date: 1411 AH _ 1990 AD, Edition: First Number of Parts 1.
- Explanation of the joint: Ya'ish bin Ali bin Ya'ish, Ibn Abi Saraya Muhammad bin Ali, Abu Al-Baqa, Muwaffaq Al-Din Al-Asadi Al-Mawsili, known as Ibn Ya'ish and Ibn Al-Sane` (d. : the first, 1422 AH - 2001 AD. Number of parts: 6.
- Explanation of the calculated introduction, Taher bin Ahmed bin Babshath (d. 469 AH), investigation: Khaled Abdel-Karim, publisher: Al-Asriya Press _ Kuwait, Edition: First, 1977 AD.
- Explanation of Facilitating Benefits, Muhammad bin Abdullah, Ibn Malik Al-Tai Al-Jiani, Abu Abdullah, Jamal Al-Din (d. 672 AH), investigation: Dr. Abdul Rahman Al-Sayed, Dr. Muhammad Badawi Al-Makhtoun, Publisher: Hajar for printing, publishing, distribution and advertising, Edition: First (1410 A.H. - 1990 A.D.), Number of Parts: 4.
- The book, Amr bin Othman bin Qanbar Al-Harithi with loyalty, Abu Bishr, nicknamed Sibawayh (died 180 AH), investigation: Abdel Salam Muhammad Harun, Publisher: Al-Khanji Library _ Cairo, Edition: Third, 1408 AH - 1988 AD, Number of Parts: 4.
- Al-Luma' in Arabic, Abu Al-Fath Othman bin Jani Al-Mawsili (d. 392 AH), investigation: Fayez Fares, publisher: Dar Al-Kutub Al-Thaqafia_Kuwait.
- Meanings of the Qur'an, Abu Zakaria Yahya bin Ziyad bin Abdullah bin Manzor Al-Dailami Al-Farra (d. 207 AH), investigation: Ahmed Youssef Al-Najati / Muhammad Ali Al-Najjar / Abdel Fattah Ismail Al-Shalabi, publisher: Dar Al-Masrya for authoring and translation - Egypt.

- Mughni Al-Labib on the books of the Arabs, Abdullah bin Youssef bin Ahmed bin Abdullah bin Youssef, Abu Muhammad, Jamal Al-Din, Ibn Hisham (d. 761 AH), investigation: Dr. Mazen Al-Mubarak / Muhammad Ali Hamdallah, Publisher: Dar Al-Fikr - Damascus, Edition: Sixth, 1985 AD.
- Al-Mofassal in the Art of Syntax, Abu Al-Qasim Mahmoud bin Amr bin Ahmed, Al-Zamakhshari Jarallah (d. 538 AH), investigation: Dr. Ali Bu Melhem, Publisher: Al-Hilal Library - Beirut - Edition: First, 1993 AD.
- The Healing Purposes in Explaining the Sufficient Summary, Abu Ishaq Ibrahim bin Musa Al-Shatibi (died 790 AH), investigation: a group of investigators, publisher: Institute of Scientific Research and Revival of Islamic Heritage at Umm Al-Qura University - Makkah Al-Mukarramah.
- Al-Muqtada in explaining the clarification: Abdul Qaher Al-Jarjani (died 471 AH), investigation: Kazem Bahr Marjan, publisher: the Ministry of Culture and Information, Dar Al-Rasheed Publishing, 1982 AD, number of parts 2.
- Al-Muqtaba: Muhammad bin Yazid bin Abdul-Akbar Al-Thamali Al-Azdi, Abu Al-Abbas, known as Al-Mubarrad (died 285 AH), investigation: Muhammad Abdul-Khaleq Azimah, publisher: Alam Al-Kutub. Beirut, number of parts: 4.
- Collection of mosques in explaining the collection of mosques, Abd al-Rahman ibn Abi Bakr, Jalal al-Din al-Suyuti (d. 911 AH), investigation: Abd al-Hamid Hindawi, publisher: Al-Tawfiqia Library - Egypt, number of parts: 3.

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